

MORPHOLOGICAL STAGES OF WORD FORMATION IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS

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Abstract : A prominent scientist Said Usmanov occupies a special place in the development of the morphology of the Uzbek language in the 20th century. S.Usmanov defended his thesis in 1953 under the guidance of linguist T.Ibragimov. This was his first serious work on morphology.

Key words: morphology, thesis, scientist, morphological structure, classification of languages, Grammatical forms of words.

Аннотация: Особое место в развитии морфологии узбекского языка в XX веке занимает видный ученый Саид Усманов. защитил кандидатскую диссертацию в 1953 году под руководством лингвиста Т.Ибрагимова. Это была его первая серьезная работа по морфологии.

Annatatsiya: XX asr o‘zbek tili morfologiyasining rivojlanishida atoqli olim Said Usmonov alohida o‘rin tutadi. tilshunos olim T.Ibragimov rahbarligida 1953 yilda nomzodlik dissertatsiyasini himoya qilgan. Bu uning morfologiyaga oid birinchi jiddiy ishi edi.

Ключевые слова: морфология, диссертация, ученый, морфологическая структура, классификация языков, грамматические формы слов.

Tayanch so‘zlar: morfologiya, dissertatsiya, olim, morfologik tuzilish, tillarning tasnifi, so‘zlarning grammatik shakllari.

I.Introduction S. Usmanov emphasizes that the approach to agglutination has a special direction. He knew that it was very important to clarify this issue in his

studies of the morphology of Turkic languages. After F. Bopp, an important feature of agglutination was the use of the first line V. The scientist notes that Humboldt expressed his views and showed the nature of the phenomenon.

S. Usmanov defines Ferdinand de Saussure as the second representative. Ferdinand de Saussure notes that three characteristics of agglutination are shown. The scientist paid special attention to representatives of the third direction, which was assessed as agglutination with the core (or base), the connection of the chain, the connection as part of the chain and the expression of grammatical meaning, A. Schleicher, V. A. Bogorodsky, V. V. He responds to the views such a scientist as Radlov.

S. Usmanov paid special attention to the grammatical form of the word. It is well known that morphology is in fact a doctrine of grammatical form. Word form, grammatical form; The scientist who made important remarks about the synthetic and analytical form determines the vocabulary of grammatical meaning and function.

II. Literature review S. Usmanov notes that attention to the morphological classification of the language began at the end of the 18th century. In European linguistics, and this took place in the eyes of Brother Schlegel, and then Stein Hahl, and J. Grimm, A. Schleicher, A. I. Thomson. The linguist who first coined the term "agglutination" in linguistics, but noted that F. Bopp created the theory of agglutination by dividing the language into two groups in the form of a flexible and agglutinative language.

The works of V.V. Reshetov, E.D. Polivanov, A.N. Kononov, S.N. Ivanov, A.M. Shcherbak serve as a scientific and methodological basis in the morphology of Uzbek linguistics of the twentieth century. Of course, it is worth noting that a special role is played by the book by Ves Reshetov, "Fundamentals of Phonetics and Grammar of the Uzbek Language" (1960). In the 1950s, scientists such as O. Kosimkhodzhaeva, B. Madvaliev, A. Khodjaev, Z. Maupov, S. Ferdaus, S. Fuzailov, A. Sulaimonov made a significant contribution to the development of morphology

in the 1960s. The famous Turkologist A.N. Kononov, who collaborated with scientists such as A. Borovkov, did a great job in this area.

III. Analysis A prominent scientist Said Usmanov occupies a special place in the development of the morphology of the Uzbek language in the 20th century. S.Usmanov defended his thesis in 1953 under the guidance of linguist T.Ibragimov. This was his first serious work on morphology.

S. Usmanov paid special attention to the grammatical form of the word. It is known that morphology is the study of grammatical form. Word form, grammatical form; the scientist who gave an important opinion about the synthetic and analytical form determines the appearance of the word form according to the grammatical meaning and function.

The work of V.V. Reshetov, E.D. Polivanov, A.N. Kononov, S.N. Ivanov, A.M. Shcherbak in the field of morphology of Uzbek linguistics of the 20th century serves as a scientific-practical and methodical basis. In this regard, it is necessary to emphasize that the book "Fundamentals of Phonetics and Grammar of the Uzbek Language" (1960) by V.V. Reshetov has a special place.

In the 1950s, scientists such as O. Kasimkhojayeva, B. Madvaliyev, A. Khojayev, Z. Ma'rupov, S. Ferdaus, S. Fuzailov, A. Sulaymonov made a great contribution to the development of the field of morphology in Uzbek linguistics. by the 60s, the famous Turkologist A.N. Kononov, who collaborated with scientists such as A. Ghulomov and A. Borovkov, did a great job in this field.

Among the important studies on the main issues of word formation in Turkic studies and Uzbek linguistics since the 50s of the 20th century, the works of A.G. Gulomov are distinguished by their deep thoughts and richness of new scientific conclusions. Using the achievements in world linguistics, the scientist who researched our rich scientific and historical sources, artistic works, folklore and dialect evidence with his own scientific method and thinking, intelligence, made a great contribution to the development of general linguistics only in the following

years. is being recognized. This recognition applies to the field of word formation in the full sense, as well as to other areas of linguistics. [2]

A.G. Gulomov evaluates such cases as follows: "the meaning of a word is related to the semantic properties of its parts" always means that the meaning of these parts is collected, and that word It does not mean the content that creates the meaning of z and is equal to it. For example, in cases such as plastering, plastering, and plastering, the meaning of the composition is born from the meaning of the parts, and the meaning of the word "andavalamak" is different from the meaning understood from the parts of the word.

Word formation, according to the scientist, is based on "simultaneity" (synchronicity) relationship, and "everytime" (diachrony) consists of a set of principles used to explain the change and development over time: "Any formation (made - made the resulting element) is not an initial ("primary"), but a subsequent (secondary) event: it is dependent (in terms of meaning and other aspects) on another event, and its semantic and structural properties are determined by that initial event. In the analysis of word formation, historical and diachronic facts are cited for comparison only where they are necessary, taken into account, but not based on. In the works of A.G. Gulomov, the phenomena of "internal form (form) of language" (V. von Humboldt) and "internal form (form) of word" (A.A. Potebnya) in general linguistics were also expressed, and the emergence of artificial words reasons, motivational reasons are noted: "A new word is born with the demand of life. This demand depends on the development of consciousness in connection with society... it is the source of birth of all innovations, dynamics, all changes. [3]

It was said that a serious study of the historical and modern morphology has also taken place. In addition, large-scale research was conducted in European and world linguistics, and all its achievements began to be applied to Uzbek linguistics.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that, as a result of the meetings and communication of great scientists such as N.A. Baskakov, A.N. Kononov, S.N.

Ivanov with Uzbek linguists, serious researchers of morphology F. Kamolov, T. Ibragimov, S. Usmonov, A.G. expanded with a number of scholars such as 'ulomov. A. Hojiyev, M. Sodikova, R. Kongurov, I. Kochkortoiev, A.H. Sulaimanov ("Helpers after the modern Uzbek literary language"), A. Abduazizov, I. Rasulov, Kh. .Komilova, A. Madgoziyev, K. Nazarov, a great researcher and enthusiast of the field of morphology were among them. Many of our scientists, such as Yo. Tojiyev, A. Berdialiyev, T. Mirzaqulov, S. Makhmatkulov, S. Sultonsaidova, started serious scientific research in the field of morphology.

After that, a number of works by the scientist in morphology were published. "A separate guide to the word and its morphological structure" (1957), "On the semantic and grammatical nature of the word repeated in the general consonant form" (1957), "On some forms of the verb" (1966), 1963, "Morphological classification of languages and agglutination in Turkic languages" (1963), "Attached speech" (1969), "Grammatical forms of words in the Uzbek language" (1964), "The problem of the use and form of word forms in the modern Uzbek language" (1963). 1964), "Morphology and functions of the word Analysis" (1965), as well as many others.

All the views of S. Usmanov on the development of the morphology of the Turkic languages as a whole, including Uzbek, are especially reflected in his fundamental study "Morphological Features of the Modern Uzbek Language". This was a study written for a doctorate. The first chapter of the work is entitled "Typological classification of languages and agglutination in Turkic languages".

Among the important studies in the field of Turkic and Uzbek linguistics from the 50s of the twentieth century, the work of G.G. Gulyamova are distinguished by deep thoughts and new scientific conclusions. It was only recently recognized that our rich scientific and historical sources, works of art, folklore and poetic arguments made a great contribution to the development of general research using scientific methods and thinking. This recognition applies, in particular, to linguistics.

I. A. Baudouin de Courten, N. V. Krushevsky, M. M. Pokrovsky, A. A. Potebnya, Theory and fabrication of relations in comparative and historical linguistics The relationship between form and content in a word has been carefully studied. In relation to the same phenomenon, the terms “anology” (I. A. Baudouin de Courten) are defined as “simplification”, “morphological redistribution” (A. A. Potebnya). its meaning is connected with the semantic nature of its components.” For example, when plaster, stucco, plaster are obtained from the meaning of the parts of the ornament, the meaning of the word “silent” is taken from the meaning of the parts. Word formation, according to the scientist, is based on “one-time” (synchronous) relationships, while “temporary” (diachronic) is a set of principles used to explain changes and development over time: not the first “), but the following (secondary) event: it depends on another event (in meaning and in other respects), its semantic and structural properties are determined by this first event. Historical, diachronic facts in word-formation analysis are given, taken into account, but not depending on where they are needed.

In the works of G. G. Gulyamov there were also references to the phenomenon of “internal form (language) of a language” (von Humboldt), “internal form (form) of a word” (A. A. Potebnya) in general linguistics, the reasons for the origin of the word and its motivation . The basics are stated: “A new word is born from the demands of life. This requirement depends on the progress of society in connection with this ... it is the source of all news, dynamics and all changes. ”

This is one of the main symbols of the sociolinguistic, pragmatic aspect of word formation: words are sporadic, logical and linguistic in nature, on which certain methods and tools are based. For this reason A.G. Gulyamov applies the concept of “word-formation model”: an abstraction model, a generalized abstract phenomenon in the sense of creating a scheme.

Here are some of them: 1) words that are not identical to the project model are similar in structure and meaning; 2) whether the word-formation models are

ineffective or not, because the model in the structure creates a new template: summing up the structure of the word structure, the word creation templates are determined, and boomodels form the word creation system.

It was said that serious studies have been conducted to study historical and modern morphology. In addition, a serious study of European and world linguistics was conducted, and all its achievements were applied to Uzbek linguistics.

IV. Discussion As a result of meetings and discussions with such great scientists as N. A. Baskakov, A. N. Kononov, S. N. Ivanov with Uzbek linguists, a number of serious morphological researchers F. Kamolov, T. Ibragimov, S. Usmanov, A. Gulamov with a scientist. A. Khodzhiev, M. Sodikova, R. Kungurov, I. Kuchkortoiev, A. Suleymanov ("Authors of the modern Uzbek literary language"), G. Abdurakhmanov ("Foundations of the modern Uzbek literary language"), Zh. Mukhtorov ("Connections in the modern Uzbek language"), B. Urinboev ("the draft category in the modern Uzbek language"), T. Khojaev ("the order of verbs in the modern Uzbek literary language"), A. Abduazizov, I. Rasulov, Kh. Kamilova, A. Madgaziev In the early 1970s M. Alamova, M. Narimanova and M. Dzhurab Eva, Yu. Tozhiev, A. Berdialiev, T. Mirzakulov, S. Mamatkulov, S. Sultonsaidova began a lot of scientific research in areas of morphology.

At the morphological stage, word formation issues are considered from the point of view of the location of morphemes, their interconnections, and the concepts of core and base are also widely used. In the framework of the second stage, the structural-semantic stage, the relationship between form (external) and content (internal) in an artificial word was widely discussed, the principles of word formation analysis, morpheme analysis and subsequent morphological analysis were presented (S.Usmanov, Sh. Rakhmatullaev, A.A. It should also be noted the merits of our leading scientists, such as Khodzhiev). In the works of A. Gulyamov, word formation is considered as a system, and the special concept of "word-formation relations" is used to explain motivation issues: In the works of such scientists as I.

A. Baudouin de Courtenay, N. V. Krushevsky, M. M. Pokrovsky, A. A. Potebnya, who developed important issues of word formation and education in the system of comparative historical linguistics and discovered new directions, the relationship of form and content in speech was studied in detail. In the studies of these scientists, it was found that the meaning in the structure of an artificial word is a reinforcing factor.

Terms such as “analogy” (I. A. Baudouin de Courtenay), “simplification”, “morphological redistribution” (A. A. Potebnya) are associated with this phenomenon. A.G. Gulyamov evaluates such cases as follows: “The idea that the meaning of a word depends on the semantic nature of its parts” does not always mean that the meaning of these parts accumulates and forms the meaning of the word, it is equal to it. ”

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For example, in cases such as plastering, plastering, plastering, the meaning of artificial comes from the meaning of the parts, while the meaning of the word andavalamoq “hasposhlamog” has a different meaning than the meaning understood from the parts. Word formation, according to the scientist, is based on a “one-time” (synchronous) relationship, and “all the time” (diachrony) consists of a set of principles used to explain the change and development of periods: primary”), but the following (secondary) event:

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In the works of A.G. the basics of motivation are noted: "A new word is born with the demands of life. This requirement depends on the development of consciousness in this regard ... it is the source of all innovation, dynamics, all changes."

V.Conclusion The point is that in A. Fulomov's work on morphonology and word formation, as well as in the book "Verb", kap-yop, bas, bot-bol-bolta-boskan; verbatim; yor-yir-jir-jar (yara), boz-bur-bush; tim-tom-dom; blind-blind; sometimes-kas-kech, etc., there are many units made of each other, connected to each other in terms of sound pairs (phonostome) and according to meaning, which form a whole system instead of 3-4. There are also laws that determine that they are made of each other. In particular, it is certain that words expressing opposite, close concepts, noun-verb pairs, noun-verb-adjective pairs, etc., were formed on the basis of special laws. The issue of the formation of new words in the form of differentiation based on phonetic change was seriously researched by A. Gulomov, and the existence of word formation in this way was justified. In our opinion, the fact that the scientist's thoughts are correct will become clearer and will be clearly

proven if the basic words, which are usually monosyllabic and have the same two sounds, are characteristic of the Uzbek language. For example, the words "jap" and "kap" are combined with the meaning "to lock"; word cutting with the meaning of "passing through the surface of something", the words "gray" with the meaning of "raw", "unprocessed", "white", the words tim-tom with the meaning of "place on top" (at the bottom of the tim), The pair yor-yir is combined with the symbol of "separation". It seems that some phonetic phenomenon happened: the previous sound was replaced in the day-night pair, etc. In all of these, on the basis of such a phonetic change, let's say that differentiation occurred and a new lexical unit was created.

The materials of the Uzbek language provide information about how new words were created in this way in history. At the end of the 20th century, at the beginning of the 21st century, there is information about the existence of one method of word formation in Uzbek linguistics, but in the speeches of most scientists in all linguistics, it began to be noted that there is no composition method of word formation[13]. Academician A. Hojiev shows the method of composition in his manual "Uzbek language word formation" published in 1989. The scientist recommended not to consider abbreviation, lexical-semantic, phonetic, syntactic-lexical methods as separate methods, and his opinions about not considering the abbreviation method as a method of word formation are well-founded. He gave excellent opinions and expressed his views on the problems of word formation, including the methods of word formation. The scientist recognized that the composition method is one of the main methods in the 80s. However, he changed his mind based on new approaches to the language system, new observations. In the "Uzbek language word formation system" manual, it gives a conclusion consisting of 3 points, noting that word formation in the composition method should not be considered as a separate method [15, 16-17]. Of course, even now, the units that are called compound words and are formed in the form of noun+adjective,

number+noun, verb+noun, imitative word+noun, noun+adjective, noun+adjective, noun+noun are formed by the "word formation method" stated that generated words do not count[16].

"Consequently, they do not belong to the object of the word formation system, the presence of more than one lexical meaningful part cannot be a sign of "compound word", a sign of composition" is debatable. Each of these must first be thoroughly justified. In particular, it is impossible not to recognize new lexical units, which are called compound words, because they are also recorded in dictionaries and grammars. But should they be called compound words or should they be called simple words considering that the process of simplification has taken place and they have become a unit representing one concept? Can the process of simplification, the simple combination of two words, create a compound word - such a lexical unit? Efforts were also made to find answers to such questions. A. Gulomov thinks about this and says that word combinations after various changes - in this way, lose their combination and become a lexical unit expressing a concept - a compound word, and even the formation of words by the recognized method of affixation is the result of further simplification of the word formation method in the first form. points out: "Historically, the way of affixation was born from the composition: stem+stem-stem+affix: the affixes actually originated from independent words: kitchen, khalkabad, anyway[10, 24-25], we know that prof.Yo.Tojiev in his "In the article on the formation of compound words in the Uzbek language [9], "Compound words are not really made from the simple addition of two words, they are usually formed by the combination of phonetic, grammatical and semantic changes of word combinations, the loss of the syntactic relationship between them, on the basis of lexicalization occurs, it can be conditionally defined as a composition method. "The formation of a compound word is not formed by the method of simple addition of words", he says and justifies it. From this it becomes clear that only the name of the

method needs to be determined. All compound words are triplicates of these compound words

Therefore, a motivated word is an important nominative-onomasiological unit, which, from the point of view of its artificial nature, shows that there are different connections between the world of concepts in the mind and the outside world. The development of society and consciousness allows the emergence of new designs as necessary.

In the early 70s, Uzbek linguistics gained great experience in studying the morphology of the Uzbek language. It is said that serious research has also appeared on the study of historical and modern morphology. In addition, a large-scale study was conducted in European and world linguistics, and all its achievements began to be applied in Uzbek linguistics.

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